

IMPLEMENTING STRATEGIES TO REDUCE HOSPITAL ACQUIRED PRESSURE ULCERS

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Background

- 2.5 million patients develop Pressure Ulcers (PU) each year
- Medicare estimates each PU adds \$42,180 in cost to a hospital stay
- HAPUs in the United States are estimated to be 1.3 to 3 million and are projected to cost \$2.2-\$3.6 billion a year
- Despite the use of established guidelines, nearly 40% of Intensive Care Unit (ICU) patients develop HAPUs
- An increase of HAPUs was noted in a community hospital's ICU unit and a quality improvement project was requested by the department manager

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project was to decrease HAPUs in a 22 bed ICU unit of a 228 bed hospital in Southern California.

Methods

- Developed and implemented a evidence-based program for pressure ulcer prevention (PUP)
- Key stakeholders included management, nursing, nutrition, medicine, wound care specialists and project champions
- Strategies for PUP included:
 - Synchronized turning schedule
 - Photographs to heels and sacrococcyx area
 - Silicone dressing to heels and sacrococcyx area

Staff Education

- Education for nursing staff included review of the PUP strategies and staging of HAPUs
- Target for post-test was 100%; individuals received additional training if needed
- Posters in unit reinforced PUP strategies

Pressure Ulcer Prevention (PUP) Framework

Evaluation Methods

- Ongoing reporting of monthly ICU HAPUs
- Trend analysis for 2015 of ICU HAPU was compared to hospital wide performance
- Trend analysis for 2015 of ICU HAPU incidence by site, interventional sites versus non-interventional sites

Results

- In 2014, 80% of HAPUs occurred at sites identified for intervention
- Of 28 HAPUs occurring in ICU during 2015
 - Nine (32.1%) HAPUs occurred at the intervention sites
 - 19 (67%) HAPUs were located on the non-targeted sites
- After initial success in HAPU reduction, an increase was noted in intervention site HAPUs during the last quarter of 2015
- Audit of PUP strategies showed 70% compliance overall in July; there were no HAPUs
- During November, overall compliance to PUP strategies decreased to 60%; there were 5 HAPUs
- Most reduced were Silicone dressing and turning every 2 hours

Conclusion

- Preliminary success of the PUP strategies achieved six months with zero HAPUs at intervention sites; yet HAPUs increased at other sites
- Maintaining focus on one objective cannot blind us to other problem occurrences
- Sustainability of change was diminished due to assignable variation: loss of key staff and institutional knowledge
- Maintaining institutional knowledge and a broad focus that includes emerging issues is critical to sustaining excellence in clinical practice in an organization

HAPU Incidence 2015

Audit of PUP Strategies

July, 2015 Compliance to the PUP strategies

	Photo heels	Photos sacrum	Dietary 24 hrs of adm	Turning q2 24 hrs of adm	Silicone Dressing on sacrum	Silicone Dressing on heels
N	26	27	27	25	19	4
Total (D)	30	30	30	26	29	29
%	87%	97%	90%	96%	63%	15%

November, 2015 Compliance to the PUP strategies

	Photo heels	Photos sacrum	Dietary 24 hrs of adm	Turning q2 24 hrs of adm	Silicone Dressing on sacrum	Silicone Dressing on heels
N	28	32	35	18	17	3
Total (D)	38	38	38	31	38	38
%	74%	84%	92%	58%	45%	8%